

Supplemental Information

Involving Girls in STEM: A Study on Gender Bias from Schooling to University

A. PRELIMINARY INTERVIEW SHORT REPORT

The preliminary interviews involved 13 female and 14 male students currently or previously enrolled in a CS Bachelor's Degree program at a major European university. The average age of the participants was 24.1 years for females and 23.8 years for males. Regarding their **current academic status**, six females and nine males were in their Bachelor's, four females and five males were in their Master's, and two males were pursuing PhD programs.

The **educational backgrounds** of the participants varied, with females coming from a mix of scientific, technical, classical, artistic, and linguistic high schools. In contrast, males predominantly came from technical institutes and scientific high schools. Notably, a higher proportion of males had prior exposure to CS through their pre-university education. Gender composition in previous classes showed that 5 out of 13 females and 11 out of 14 males were in male-dominated environments.

Motivations for enrolling in CS varied, with both genders citing continued studies and future job prospects as primary reasons. Females also highlighted curiosity and a passion for computers and programming, with some noting family influence and an interest in web development. Males also mentioned the impact of online content and the desire to develop software.

Gender-related issues identified included instances of bias and inappropriate behavior from peers and professors, which females more frequently reported as behaviors guided by gender stereotypes. Males perceived such issues less severely, often viewing them erroneously as jokes.

Both groups believed in an increasing **future presence of women in STEM fields**.

Recommendations to address gender disparity included cultural interventions from early childhood

through university, promoting female role models, and offering more practical and interdisciplinary CS courses. This study underscores the importance of early and sustained efforts to encourage women in CS, suggesting that future research should develop strategies to foster gender equality.

B. QUESTIONNAIRE

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1. Your age: _____
2. Your gender:
 male female non-binary
3. Indicate in which year you matriculated: _____
4. Indicate where you are in your course of study

<input type="checkbox"/> First year bachelor's degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Second year master's degree
<input type="checkbox"/> Second year bachelor's degree	<input type="checkbox"/> I dropped out of my master's degree
<input type="checkbox"/> Third year bachelor's degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Outside the prescribed time of master's degree course
<input type="checkbox"/> I dropped out of my bachelor's degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Master's degree graduate
<input type="checkbox"/> Outside prescribed time of bachelor's degree course	<input type="checkbox"/> First year of PhD
<input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor's degree graduate	<input type="checkbox"/> Second year of PhD
<input type="checkbox"/> First year master's degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Third year of PhD
	<input type="checkbox"/> Completed PhD

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN SECONDARY SCHOOL EDUCATION

5. Indicate what higher education you have had:
 Technical institute
 Scientific secondary school
 Classical secondary school
 Artistic secondary school
 Linguistic secondary school
 Vocational school
 Other _____
6. While studying in secondary school...
 most of the class was male
 the class was divided equally into males and females
 most of the class was female
7. Did you study computer science in secondary school?
 Yes
 No

GENDER DIFFERENCES AT THE TIME OF CS UNIVERSITY COURSE ENROLLMENT

8. Why did you enroll in computer science? (select up to three answers)

- Continue with studies from secondary school
- Curiosity
- Passion for computers
- Passion for programming
- Passion for video games
- Advice from an acquaintance/friend/relative
- Have good job opportunities after graduation
- Have a future job compatible with starting a family
- Other

9. When you enrolled, how prepared did you feel compared to your classmates?

1	2	3	4	5
Not at all				Very much

10. When you enrolled, how prepared were you in programming?

1	2	3	4	5
I didn't know anything				I knew everything; the first year was a refresher of what I already knew

11. When you enrolled was there any first year course that particularly scared you?

- Mathematical analysis
- English
- Computer architecture
- Logic
- Algebra and discrete mathematics
- Programming
- Operating systems
- None
- Every course

GENDER DIFFERENCES DURING CS UNIVERSITY COURSES

12. Which course was the most difficult of all of your three-year course among those you followed?

- Mathematical analysis
- English
- Computer architecture
- Logic
- Algebra and discrete mathematics
- Programming
- Operating systems
- Algorithms and data structures
- Cybersecurity: principles and practices
- Probability and statistics
- Object-oriented programming
- Computer networks
- Automata and formal languages
- Databases
- Numerical calculation
- Law, information technology and society
- Introduction to machine learning
- Methods and technologies for software development
- Programming paradigms
- Software engineering
- Operational research
- Web technologies
- None

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN PERCEIVING GENDER STEREOTYPES

13. Do you think girls/women are disadvantaged in CS?

1	2	3	4	5
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No, not at all Yes, absolutely

14- In your opinion, is the idea "*CS is for men*" present among young people/adults (15-40 years old)?

1	2	3	4	5
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No, not at all Yes, very much

15. In your opinion, is the idea "*CS is for men*" present among adults/elderly (+40 years old)?

1	2	3	4	5
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No, not at all Yes, very much

FUTURE OF WOMEN IN CS: HOW CAN THE GAP BE NARROWED?

16. What do you think about the future? In 20 years, in the IT field...

- 0= There will be fewer women than today
- 1= The same number of genders as they are today will remain
- 2= There will be more women than today, but always fewer than men
- 3= The number of women will be equal to that of men
- 4= There will be more women than today, even more than men
- I don't know

17. In your opinion, how can the number of girls/women in CS be increased? Please indicate how much you agree with the following suggestions

	1 = Totally disagree	2	3	4	5 = Totally agree
Educational intervention for families against cultural bias					
Intervention in kindergarten/elementary schools against cultural bias					
Intervention in middle school before choosing secondary school by introducing the CS discipline					
Intervention in secondary schools with practical campus initiatives/projects/competitions in the CS field					
Intervention in secondary schools by further integrating the CS discipline into all school curricula					
Intervention before university choice with open days/open lessons/stands in which both male and female students/CS professors are involved					
Create female quotas/scholarships for female students to access the CS faculty					
Create women's events/conferences with successful women in CS					
Create a women's group representing female students within the department					
The number of girls/women in CS cannot be increased because the academic choice depends on the attitudes of the women themselves					
The number of girls/women in CS cannot be increased because it remains a male field					

C. ADDITIONAL ANALYSIS RESULTS

Complete results of the analysis reported in the main text.

Table S1

Number of Students and Relative Standardized Residuals (z) of the χ^2 Analysis of the Association Between Gender and Different Types of Secondary Schools Attended by CS Students

	Females	z	Males	z	Total sample
Technical institute	10	-2.11	79	1.13	87
Scientific secondary school	22	1.93	44	-1.03	66
Other school	5	1.08	9	-0.58	14
Total	37		130		167

Table S2

Number of Students and Relative Standardized Residuals (z) of the χ^2 Analysis of the Association Between Gender and Different Types of Secondary Classes' Gender Distribution

	Females	z	Males	z	Total sample
Mostly male class	21	-1.08	103	0.58	124
Gender balanced class	9	0.43	23	-0.23	32
Mostly female class	7	2.92	4	-1.56	11
Total	37		130		167

Table S3

Distribution of Reasons for Enrolling in the Bachelor's Degree Program in Computer Science According to Gender

Reasons for enrollment	Females	Males	Total sample	Difference between genders
Continue with studies from secondary school	9	60	69	$\chi^2 = 5.66, p < .05, OR = 0.38, 95\% CI \text{ for } OR [0.16, 0.86]$
Curiosity	15	19	34	$\chi^2 = 11.94, p < .001, OR = 3.98, 95\% CI \text{ for } OR [1.76, 9.02]$
Passion for computers	14	69	83	$\chi^2 = 2.68, p = .10$
Passion for programming	16	78	94	$\chi^2 = 3.29, p = .07$
Passion for video games	2	30	32	FET $p < .05, OR = 0.19, 95\% CI \text{ for } OR [0.02, 0.82]$
Advice from an acquaintance/friend/relative	3	8	11	FET $p = .71, OR = 1.34$
Have good job opportunities after graduation	23	63	86	$\chi^2 = 2.17, p = .14$
Have a future job compatible with starting a family	3	8	11	FET $p = .71, OR = 1.34$
Other	3	5	8	FET $p = .38, OR = 2.19$

Note. The last column reports the statistics related to the difference between males and females, where significant results are reported in bold.

Table S4

Distribution of Participants in the First Year of Pursuing the Bachelor's Degree Program in Computer Science in Relation to Educational Courses That Intimidated Them the Most When They Enrolled

First-year courses	Females	Males	Total	%	Difference between genders
Mathematical analysis	15	99	114	68.26	$\chi^2 = 16.86, p < .001, OR = 0.21, 95\% CI$ for OR [0.10, 0.46]
English	0	2	2	1.20	<i>FET</i> $p = 1.00, OR = 0.00$
Computer architecture	4	3	7	4.19	<i>FET</i> $p < .05, OR = 5.07, 95\% CI$ for OR [0.81, 36.28]
Logic	0	3	3	1.80	<i>FET</i> $p = 1.00, OR = 0.00$
Algebra and discrete mathematics	1	19	20	11.98	<i>FET</i> $p = .08, OR = 0.16$
Programming	23	23	46	27.55	$\chi^2 = 28.54, p < .001, OR = 7.64, 95\% CI$ for OR [3.43, 17.06]
Operating systems	3	4	7	4.19	<i>FET</i> $p = 0.18, OR = 2.76$
No courses	5	18	23	13.77	$\chi^2 = 0.00, p = .96$
Every course	0	1	1	0.60	<i>FET</i> $p = 1.00, OR = 0.00$

Note: The last column reports the statistics related to the difference between males and females, where significant results are reported in bold.

Table S5

Distribution of Graduate Participants Among all Courses Pursing the Bachelor's Degree in Computer Science Program in Response to the Question of Which Course was the Most Difficult

Bachelor's degree courses	Females	Males	Total	%	Difference between genders
Mathematical analysis	3	12	15	21.74	<i>FET</i> $p = 0.53$, <i>OR</i> = 0.60
English	1	0	1	1.45	<i>FET</i> $p = 0.28$, <i>OR</i> = ∞
Programming	7	7	14	20.29	$\chi^2 = 4.44$, $p < .05$, <i>OR</i> = 3.58, 95% CI for <i>OR</i> [1.05, 12.23]
Algorithms and data structures	0	1	1	1.45	<i>FET</i> $p = 1.00$, <i>OR</i> = 0.00
Object-oriented programming	2	2	4	5.80	<i>FET</i> $p = .30$, <i>OR</i> = 2.77
Automata and formal languages	1	1	2	2.90	<i>FET</i> $p = .48$, <i>OR</i> = 2.68
Numerical calculation	0	9	9	13.04	<i>FET</i> $p = .06$, <i>OR</i> = 0.00
Software engineering	4	18	22	31.88	<i>FET</i> $p = .27$, <i>OR</i> = 0.48
None	1	0	1	1.45	<i>FET</i> $p = .28$, <i>OR</i> = ∞

Note. Other courses were not included because they were not chosen by any participant (courses: computer architecture; logic; algebra and discrete mathematics; operating systems; law, information technology and society; cybersecurity: principles and practices; probability and statistics; introduction to machine learning; methods and technologies for software development; programming paradigms; computer networks; databases; operational research; web technologies). The last column reports the statistics related to the difference between males and females, where significant results are reported in bold.

Intermediate steps of the multiple linear regression reported in Table 5 of the main text.

Model 1 (intercept): $RMSE = 1.21$; **Model 2** (intercept + passion for programming): $F\text{-change}_{(1, 35)} = 16.61, p < .001, R^2 = 0.32, Adjusted R^2 = 0.30, RMSE = 1.01, ANOVA F_{(1, 35)} = 16.61, p < .001$; **Model 3** (intercept + passion for programming + CS is for men > 40 years old): $F\text{-change}_{(1, 34)} = 14.95, p < .001, R^2 = 0.53, Adjusted R^2 = 0.50, RMSE = 0.85, ANOVA F_{(2, 34)} = 19.09, p < .001$; **Model 4** (intercept + passion for programming + CS is for men > 40 years old + continue with studies from secondary school): $F\text{-change}_{(1, 33)} = 10.89, p < .01, R^2 = 0.65, Adjusted R^2 = 0.61, RMSE = 0.69, ANOVA F_{(3, 33)} = 20.06, p < .001$.

Intermediate steps of the multiple linear regression reported in Table 6 of the main text.

Model 1 (intercept): $RMSE = 1.24$; **Model 2** (intercept + CS in secondary school): $F\text{-change}_{(1, 35)} = 16.05, p < .001, R^2 = 0.31, Adjusted R^2 = 0.30, RMSE = 1.04, ANOVA F_{(1, 35)} = 16.05, p < .001$; **Model 3** (intercept + CS in secondary school + passion for programming): $F\text{-change}_{(1, 34)} = 13.97, p < .001, R^2 = 0.51, Adjusted R^2 = 0.49, RMSE = 0.88, ANOVA F_{(2, 34)} = 17.99, p < .001$; **Model 4** (intercept + CS in secondary school + passion for programming + continue with studies from secondary school): $F\text{-change}_{(3, 33)} = 11.15, p < .001, R^2 = 0.64, Adjusted R^2 = 0.60, RMSE = 0.78, ANOVA F_{(3, 33)} = 19.29, p < .001$; **Model 5** (intercept + CS in secondary school + passion for programming + continue with studies from secondary school + passion for computers): $F\text{-change}_{(4, 32)} = 11.31, p < .001, R^2 = 0.73, Adjusted R^2 = 0.70, RMSE = 0.68, ANOVA F_{(4, 32)} = 21.81, p < .001$.

Table S6

Male and Female Students' Answers Concerning How to Increase the Number of Female Students Enrolled in Computer Science Bachelor's Degree Programs

Possible initiatives to increase females' number in CS	Females		Males		Total		Difference between genders
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	
Educational intervention for families against cultural bias	3.41	1.32	3.38	1.33	3.38	1.32	$t_{(165)} = -0.12, p = .91, d = -0.02, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.39, 0.34)$
Intervention in kindergarten/elementary schools against cultural bias	3.70	1.43	3.61	1.34	3.63	1.36	$t_{(165)} = -0.37, p = .71, d = -0.07, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.44, 0.30)$
Intervention in middle school before choosing secondary school by introducing the CS discipline	4.27	0.96	4.00	1.19	4.06	1.14	$t_{(165)} = -1.27, p = .21, d = -0.24, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.60, 0.13)$
Intervention in secondary schools with practical campus initiatives/projects/competitions in the CS field	4.05	1.00	3.79	1.26	3.84	1.21	$t_{(165)} = -1.20, p = .23, d = -0.22, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.59, 0.14)$
Intervention in secondary schools by further integrating the CS discipline into all school curricula	4.03	1.17	3.79	1.25	3.84	1.23	$t_{(165)} = -1.06, p = .29, d = -0.20, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.56, 0.17)$
Intervention before university choice with open days/open lessons/stands in which both male and female students/CS professors are involved	3.68	1.27	3.38	1.31	3.44	1.31	$t_{(165)} = -1.23, p = .22, d = -0.23, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.60, 0.14)$
Create female quotas/scholarships for female students to access the CS faculty	2.46	1.59	1.87	1.10	2.00	1.25	$t_{(165)} = -2.58, p < .05, d = -0.48, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.85, -0.11)$
Create women's events/conferences with successful women in CS	3.41	1.38	2.98	1.33	3.07	1.35	$t_{(165)} = -1.71, p = .09, d = -0.32, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.69, 0.05)$
Create a women's group representing female students within the department	2.49	1.45	2.17	1.21	2.24	1.27	$t_{(165)} = -1.35, p = .18, d = -0.25, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.62, 0.12)$
The number of girls/women in CS cannot be increased because the academic choice depends on the attitudes of the women themselves	2.38	1.32	2.43	1.43	2.42	1.40	$t_{(165)} = 0.20, p = .84, d = 0.04, 95\% \text{ CI for Cohen's } d (-0.33, 0.40)$

The number of girls/women in CS cannot be increased because it remains a male field	1.11	0.39	1.15	0.58	1.14	0.54	<i>U = 2418.00, p = .92, r = 0.01, 95% CI for Rank-Biserial Correlation (-4.839e -6, 3.315e -5)</i>
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Note. The last column reports the statistics related to the difference between males and females, where significant results are highlighted in bold.